

Effect of V₂O₅ loading on the degradation of malachite green using ZnO/SiO₂ nano-photocatalyst

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Abstract : In this contribution, ZnO/SiO₂ was prepared using sol-gel method, and vanadium particles were loaded on this nano-photocatalyst by wet incipient method. They characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive (EDX) analysis and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR). The XRD patterns showed that the zinc oxide samples have a wurtzite structure (hexagonal phase) and vanadium doped is in V₂O₅ crystalline structure. The particle sizes were calculated using Scheerer's equation and were around 32 nm. For photocatalytic test, decomposition of Malachite Green Oxalate (MG), as an organic pollutant, was carried out. A comparison of degradation between bare catalyst and vanadium loaded ZnO/SiO₂ under UV-Vis light irradiation shows that the V₂O₅-ZnO/SiO₂ is more efficient than bare one.

Keywords : Photocatalyst, malachite green, UV-Vis, ZnO, V₂O₅.

Introduction

Various pollutants may be found in the water, soil and air which exert deleterious effects on human health, plants and animals and thus affect the natural environment. Water contamination caused by various chemical substances produced in different plants and penetrated into the surface water, groundwater, or even the air, is a major threat to the environment and water decontamination is one of the important challenges of the human life. Therefore, a wide range of activities are taking place to treat industrial effluents and remove their pollutants before entering to the environment¹⁻⁴.

Elimination of persistent organic pollutants that remain for a long time in the environment is one of the most difficult processes of the effluent treatment. Many methods are employed to remove or destroy the pollutants of effluents and contaminating gases. Some destructive methods use strong oxidants which are harmful. On the other hand, currently used non-destructive methods

bring also serious losses. For example, air stripping (a method for the removal of volatile organic compounds from surface water or groundwater in which air is blown into water and the contaminants are evaporated into air) converts water contamination to the air pollution. Carbon adsorption (eliminating volatile and non-volatile chemicals) produces a harmful solid which should be destroyed. One of the weaknesses of these old processes is that the pollutants are not destroyed, but displaced from one phase to another. Therefore, methods for destruction of organic pollutants should be replaced with methods exerting less or negligible harms on the environment¹⁻⁶.

Low rate of metallic oxides photocatalysis in the degradation reactions has necessitated the synthesis of new photocatalysts; and researchers have started to study various properties such as crystalline structure, particle size, band gap, surface area, and different beds. Synthesis of nano-size particles is a method to increase the surface area of a photocatalyst to enable the reactive sites on its

surface to be increased. To increase the active centers of a catalyst, it can be covered on a stabilizer such as silica⁷⁻¹⁰.

The use of ultraviolet light for destroying pollutants by photocatalysts is a limitation for industry which can be overcome by reducing the band gap, because photocatalysts are semiconductor. A method for reducing the band gap is to dope metals such as platinum, vanadium, silver etc. into the structure of photocatalysts¹¹⁻¹⁶.

In this work, the preparation results of two nano-photocatalysts: ZnO/SiO₂ and V₂O₅-ZnO/SiO₂ have been reported¹⁷. Also, the photocatalytic decomposition of Malachite green oxalate as an organic dye pollutant using two photocatalysts under UV/Vis illumination has been investigated.

Materials and methods :

All materials used in this work were purchased from Merck and used without modification.

Preparation of ZnO nanoparticles :

In a typical synthesis, a solution of 5 mmol zinc acetate dihydrate in 30 mL absolute ethanol was added to a solution of surfactant CTAB (Zn(Ac)₂·2H₂O to CTAB molar ratio was equal to 1) in 30 mL of absolute ethanol under stirring. Then, 20 mL of NaOH (0.3 M) solution was added to the above solution under continuous stirring in order to get the pH value of solution about 10. The new solution was kept in a water bath at 70 °C for 2 h. It was observed that the solution started precipitating after one hour in water bath. After cooling the system to room temperature, the product was separated by centrifugation, washed with absolute ethanol and deionized water for several times, and then dried under vacuum at 70 °C for 10 h. Finally, the nanoparticles were calcined at 750 °C for 3 h.

Preparation of nano-photocatalyst ZnO/SiO₂ :

pH of 20 ml of a suspension containing 0.01 mole ZnO was adjusted on 9-10 through dropping NaOH 0.3 M. This mixture refluxed after severe stirring for 10 h at 70 °C until stable zinc hydroxide sols were formed. After the reflux was finished, some tetraethyl orthosilicate was dropped on the sol at the same temperature to achieve a mole ratio of zinc to silicon of 30 to 70. The formed sol was held in the vacuum at room temperature for two

days. Then it was calcined in a 400 °C furnace for 3 h.

Doping of vanadium into ZnO/SiO₂ :

First, 50 ml of deionized water was added to 3 g of ZnO/SiO₂ and stirred for one hour to obtain a uniform suspension. Then, the amount of ammonium metavanadate (V/Zn = 0.1) was added to this suspension under vigorously stirring at 70 °C until the yellow paste obtained. The dough was placed in a 70 °C vacuum oven overnight. The resulting yellow solid catalyst was calcined at 400 °C for 2 h.

Degradation of malachite green dye using the synthesized catalysts :

Suspensions containing 150 ml of 10 ppm malachite green dye together with ZnO/SiO₂ and V₂O₅-ZnO/SiO₂ catalysts with a concentration of 0.2, 0.3, and 0.4 g/L (pH of the suspensions was stabilized at 3, 4, 5, and 6), a magnetic stirrer, and an air flow which was blown into a reactor through a tube to uniform the environment were used in each experiment. The reactor consisted of two tungsten lamps; those with wavelength of 220-230 nm was used for irradiation at UV range and those with wavelength of 500-700 nm for irradiation at visible range.

It should be noted that in the experiments to optimize the amount of catalyst and the environment pH, the irradiation time was 120 min.

Before irradiation, all solutions were stirred for 30 min in the dark to balance absorption and desorption of pollutants on the catalyst surface. A UV-Vis spectrophotometer was used to study the degradation of pollutants. Thus the absorption spectra of the samples were measured at certain intervals and the amount of the pollutant removal or its conversion to another substance was evaluated by the decrease in intensity of the relevant absorption peak.

Characterization :

The crystal phase and particle size of the synthesized products were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using FK60-04 with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$), and with instrumental setting of 35 kV and 20 mA. The morphology of the nanostructures was observed by emission scanning electron microscopy (SEM, PHILIPS-XL ϕ 30). Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra were recorded on a SHIMADZU-840S spectrophotometer using KBr

pellet. BET analysis was carried out with QUANTASORB. UV-Vis Diffuse Reflectance Spectra (DRS) were obtained for the dry-pressed disk samples using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (SHIMADZU-2550). The amount of degradation of the malachite green was investigated measuring the absorption intensity of the malachite green remained in the solution by means of UV-Vis spectroscopy (SHIMADZU-2550).

Results and discussion

Structural analysis of the catalysts :

The XRD patterns of bare ZnO nanoparticles (a), ZnO@SiO₂ (b) and V₂O₅-ZnO/SiO₂ nanophotocatalysts (c) are shown in Fig. 1. All peaks can be well indexed to wurtzite structure (hexagonal phase) with lattice constants of $a = 0.32495$ nm and $c = 0.52069$ nm (JCPDS, No. 36-1451). No other crystalline phase was found in the XRD patterns, indicating the high purity of the products. The particles sizes can be calculated using Scherrer's equation : $D = 0.9 \lambda / (\beta \cos \theta)$ where λ is the X-ray wavelength (1.54 Å), β is the full-width at half-maximum intensity of the diffraction line and θ is the diffraction angle. The crystallites sizes are estimated to be around 32 nm. Also the surface area of 358 m²/g was obtained for ZnO catalyst calcined at 750 °C temperature.

In Fig. 1b a board new peak is appeared at diffraction degree about 22°, which presents the SiO₂ amorphous state in the product. Fig. 1c shows the XRD pattern of vanadium doped ZnO/SiO₂ sample. In Fig. 1c three new peaks are appeared at diffraction degrees 15.37°, 20.29° and 26.20°, which can be well indexed to V₂O₅ crystalline structure (JCPDS, No. 41-1426). Therefore it can be concluded that the V₂O₅-loaded ZnO/SiO₂ is carried out successfully.

The FT-IR spectra of ZnO, ZnO/SiO₂ and V₂O₅-doped ZnO/SiO₂ nanoparticles are shown in Figs. 2(a-c). The vibrational peaks in the range of 3600–3650 cm⁻¹ and 1600–1650 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to the stretching and bending vibrations of structural hydroxyl groups of the adsorbed water. The peak in the range of 420–450 cm⁻¹ can be associated to the stretching vibration mode of the Zn-O¹⁸⁻²⁰. The peaks in the ranges of 1050–1110 cm⁻¹ and 750–800 cm⁻¹ in Figs. 2(b-c) are corresponded to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibration modes of

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of (a) ZnO, (b) ZnO/SiO₂ and (c) V₂O₅-ZnO/SiO₂ samples.

the Si-O-Si, respectively, and are absent in Fig. 2a. The peak which is appeared at 440–480 cm⁻¹ is due to the

Fig. 2. FT-IR spectra of (a) ZnO, (b) ZnO/SiO₂ and (c) V₂O₅-ZnO/SiO₂ samples.

bending vibration mode of Si-O-Si^{21,22}. Also, the peaks which are appeared at 610, 815 and 1023 cm⁻¹ are due to the stretching vibration mode of V-O, the bending vibration mode of V-O-V and the stretching vibration mode of V=O, respectively, and are absent in Figs. 2(a-b)²³⁻²⁵. These results clearly show that V₂O₅ is successfully loaded on the ZnO nanoparticles. This is in agreement with the results of XRD patterns.

The morphology of the products was observed by SEM images. The SEM images of ZnO, and V₂O₅-doped ZnO/SiO₂ nanoparticles are shown in Figs. 3(a-b), respectively.

Fig. 3. SEM images of (a) bare ZnO and (b) V₂O₅-ZnO/SiO₂ nanoparticles.

The energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analyses of prepared samples are shown in Figs. 4(a-b). The EDX analysis of ZnO sample confirms that the product consists of Zn and O (Fig. 4a). Also, the EDX analysis of V₂O₅-doped ZnO/SiO₂ sample confirms the presence of V and Si in

the product (Fig. 4b). These results are consistent with the XRD and FT-IR data.

Fig. 4. EDX spectra of (a) bare ZnO and (b) V_2O_5 -ZnO/SiO₂ nanoparticles.

Photocatalytic activity :

Degradation of malachite green dye using ZnO/SiO₂ and V₂O₅-ZnO/SiO₂ photocatalysts under UV irradiation :

Malachite green dye has three absorption bands at wavelengths of 617, 424, and 316 nm which are related to the transfers of $\pi \rightarrow \pi$ of the aromatic ring induced by *N*-methyl groups attached to them, and $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ and $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$ of the aromatic ring, respectively (Fig. 5). The mechanism of malachite green dye degradation proceeds through

Fig. 5. UV-Vis spectrum of malachite green (10 ppm).

either conjugated structure degradation or dimethyl removal. If decrease in the absorption intensity during the reaction is associated with a shift of the absorption peak (617 nm) toward shorter wavelengths, the reaction proceeds through dimethyl removal. The reason for this shift is the removal of *N,N*-dimethyl chromophore which is an electron donor and its gradual elimination during degradation results in the absorption range of aromatic system to shift toward shorter wavelengths. If the maximum peak intensity gradually decreases without any shift in the absorption wavelength, the reaction proceeds through the conjugated structure degradation²⁶.

Figs. 6–9 show the degradation of malachite green dye at pH range of 3–6 on ZnO/SiO₂ (0.3 g/L). As seen in the general pattern of the spectra, the absorption amount of malachite green dye on this catalyst is directly related to the pH increment. To justify this increase, it can be noted that the pH_{zcp} of the catalyst is 8.7 and at pH below pH_{zcp} the catalyst surface is positively charged, thus it has more potential to attract negatively charged ions. By increasing pH and its approximation to pH_{zcp} , negative charges are gradually increased on the catalyst surface, and therefore, malachite green dye with an unstable positive charge is better absorbed by the catalyst.

Along with the degradation progress and reduction of the maximum absorption wavelength intensity, a shift toward lower wavelengths can be seen in all UV-Vis absorption spectra shown in the Figures of malachite green dye degradation at pH 3–6. The reason for this shift is the elimination of *N,N*-dimethyl chromophore. As mentioned earlier, this chromophore is an electron donor,

Fig. 6. Photodegradation of MG on bare ZnO/SiO₂ photocatalyst at pH 3.

Fig. 7. Photodegradation of MG on bare ZnO/SiO₂ photocatalyst at pH 4.

Fig. 8. Photodegradation of MG on bare ZnO/SiO₂ photocatalyst at pH 5.

thus following the process, the absorption wavelength of the aromatic system is shifted toward higher wavelengths and after its gradual elimination during degradation, the absorption range of the aromatic system is shifted toward shorter wavelengths.

With the progress of the degradation process and 30 min after initiation of the reaction, some peaks were quickly appeared in the ranges of 350–370 and 230–250 nm. The peak at 350–370 nm cannot be attributed to a stable product during the reaction, because, as is shown in Figs. 6–9 and in particular Fig. 8, this peak is more like a shoulder rather than a clear peak, representing the generation of an intermediate. After an hour and degradation of the intermediate, no specific shift was appeared at 350–370 nm, concluding that its degradation is not associated with the removal of chromophore. The intermediate reaches its maximum amount one hour after initiation of the reaction and then its resorption and destruction begins following depletion of the catalyst active centers. The degradation rate of this intermediate is directly related to the degradation rate of malachite green (rate of the maximum peak disappearance), because faster degradation of malachite green, deplete more the catalyst active centers which enable them to absorb the intermediates. At pH 5, the peak is completely removed over two hours. The other peak in the range 230–250 nm with a fluctuating value (adsorption and desorption), is likely to be the products of degradation. According to the degradation reactions of malachite green in the presence of

Fig. 9. Photodegradation of MG on bare ZnO/SiO₂ photocatalyst at pH 6.

ZnO/SiO_2 (0.3 g/L) at pH 3–6, the highest photocatalytic activity of ZnO/SiO_2 was realized at pH 5.

The optimum amount of ZnO/SiO_2 and appropriate pH of the solution for degradation of 150 ml malachite green dye with a concentration of 10 ppm were obtained 0.3 g/L and 5, respectively, (Tables 1 and 2).

Table 1. The results of photodegradation of MG (%) on ZnO/SiO_2 photocatalyst (0.2, 0.3 and 0.4 g/L) at pH 5

The amount of ZnO/SiO_2 (g/L), pH 5	The degradation of MG (%)
0.2	72.5
0.3	99.3
0.4	74.3

Table 2. The results of photodegradation of MG (%) on ZnO/SiO_2 photocatalyst (0.3 g/L) at pH 3, 4, 5 and 6

pH (The amount of $ZnO/SiO_2 = 0.3$ g/L)	The degradation of MG (%)
3	22.4
4	63.3
5	99.3
6	67.2

Fig. 10 shows the variation of malachite green spectrum treated through heterogeneous photocatalysis with 0.3 g/L V_2O_5-ZnO/SiO_2 at pH 5 (optimal conditions) for 90 min. The reduction rate of maximum absorption and the variation of dye concentration are quite obvious from the spectra. As seen, the absorption initial amount of the

Fig. 10. Photodegradation of MG on V_2O_5-ZnO/SiO_2 photocatalyst at pH 5.

dye is more in this catalyst than ZnO/SiO_2 , while UV-Vis spectra pattern of both pure and doped catalysts are like each other. Higher dye adsorption of V_2O_5-ZnO/SiO_2 is due to low pH_{zcp} of this catalyst (4.6). In addition, alteration of the dye concentration from spectra shows that the destructive reaction of malachite green on V_2O_5-ZnO/SiO_2 occurs faster than ZnO/SiO_2 under UV irradiation. This is due to the presence of vanadium. As we know, doped metal ions affect optical activity through trapping electrons or holes and altering the reproduction rate of e^-/h^{+27} .

Degradation of malachite green dye with ZnO/SiO_2 and V_2O_5-ZnO/SiO_2 photocatalysts under visible light :

ZnO/SiO_2 has a large band gap and hence is not able to perform photocatalysis reaction in the visible light.

Fig. 11 shows changes in the absorption spectra of malachite green by V_2O_5-ZnO/SiO_2 under visible light. As seen in this figure, changes in the absorption spectra of malachite green catalyst by V_2O_5-ZnO/SiO_2 under visible light is similar to the degradation mechanism under UV radiation. The reaction is continued for about 120 min and malachite green is completely degraded by V_2O_5-ZnO/SiO_2 under visible light. Given the band gap distance of zinc oxide (3.37 eV), the activity of ZnO/SiO_2 in the visible light is minimal, while doping of V_2O_5 in ZnO network displaced the band gap toward longer wavelengths (visible light) and increased the photocatalysis activity in the range of visible light. UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spec-

Fig. 11. Photodegradation of MG on V_2O_5-ZnO/SiO_2 photocatalyst at pH 5 (under visible light).

tra of catalysts (Fig. 12) confirm the reduction of V_2O_5 -ZnO/SiO₂ band gap compared to ZnO/SiO₂.

Fig. 12. UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectra of (a) ZnO/SiO₂ and (b) V₂O₅-ZnO/SiO₂ nanoparticles.

Conclusions

ZnO/SiO₂ nanocomposite was prepared using sol-gel method, and vanadium particles were successfully loaded on this nano-photocatalyst by wet incipient method. The results were found that the amount of adsorbed malachite green dye on this catalyst is directly related to the pH increment. The optimum amount of ZnO/SiO₂ and appropriate pH of the solution for degradation of 150 ml malachite green dye with a concentration of 10 ppm were obtained 0.3 g/L and 5, respectively. In optimal conditions, alteration of the dye concentration from spectra shows that the destructive reaction of malachite green on V₂O₅-ZnO/SiO₂ occurs faster than ZnO/SiO₂ under UV irradiation. Also, the activity of ZnO/SiO₂ in the visible light is minimal, while doping of V₂O₅ in ZnO network displaced the band gap toward longer wavelengths (visible light) and increased the photocatalysis activity in the range of visible light. The results of the photocatalytic test reveal that V₂O₅-ZnO/SiO₂ may be an extremely viable adsorbent for application in the treatment of water and industrial wastewater contaminated with dyes.

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